

Let's care

BUILDING SAFE AND CARING SCHOOLS
TO FOSTER EDUCATIONAL INCLUSION
AND SCHOOL ACHIEVEMENT

LET'S CARE

D6.1. Project's website

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DOCUMENT CONTRIBUTORS

Deliverable responsible	13-IPA	
Contributors	Organisation	
LUCA LASZLO	IPA	
ELENA MILLI	POLO	
STEFANO COBELLO	POLO	
Reviewers	Organisation	
MERCEDES FERNÁNDEZ	COM	
EVA BAJO	COM	
ABEL MUÑIZ	ZIC	
CAROLINA SIMÓN	ZIC	
OLATZ MIRANDA	ZIC	

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1. Executive Summary

This report includes a brief description of the project's website alongside with the visual identity defined for the LET'S CARE project, with the aim of defining and providing general instructions about the visual layout of the project.

The visual identity of LET'S CARE project aims at enhancing visibility and recognition of the project thanks to a clear and identifiable appearance in all printed and online materials.

The different elements forming the LET'S CARE Visual Identity are described in the following pages.

2. LET'S CARE website

The website of the LET'S CARE project has been created under the domain <https://letsproject.eu/> and a first look at the website can be observed in Figure 1.

Figure 1 - Project's website

This website will be the main starting point for all communication, exploitation, dissemination and up-scaling of project activities. Moreover, the website will be a fundamental information tool for the interested users by presenting:

- general information about the project,
- the Consortium,
- LET'S CARE public deliverables (with download links),
- access to the LET'S CARE Hub,
- news and activities of the project,
- external links of related sites,
- policy, research and practice.

Although available from M3 of the project, the website will be updated and maintained throughout the project period and sustained for a minimum of 5 years after the project ends.

2.1. The website functions as the showcase of the project's activities and results, providing information to the public, predominantly in a unidirectional way. Its main purpose is supporting the communication of the project's activities through online contents and media, while in parallel the LET'S CARE Hub (T1.4) provides the basis for the community of stakeholders, enabling access to relevant materials, and facilitating collaboration, knowledge sharing, exchange of ideas and experiences, and community-building among project stakeholders. In this manner, the website is the gateway to LET'S CARE Hub, which will offer the stakeholders a discussion/co-creative/collaborative space revolving around the project's specific developments. The Hub is designed to facilitate the interactive communication, community engagement, and meaningful conversations among the participants of the Community of Schools (T1.2) and LET'S CARE Network of Stakeholders (T1.3). In turn, the website is the access point for outreach, information, and public awareness.

The following table further details the comparison¹.

	WEBSITE	HUB
Aims	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Make the project visible and visually identifiable online. • Departing contact point for the general public. • Portal for general information, documentation and updates of the project. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Engagement of and co-creation with stakeholders • Repository resources and tools developed within the project. Specific documentation and focus on the project's outputs that promote influencing educational practices and policies.
Key contributions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • LET'S CARE project visibility. • Public documentation of the project 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Active engagement of stakeholders and promotion of capability-building for co-

¹ For a detailed overview of the strategic and operational differences between the two portal, consult D1.5. LET'S CARE Hub platform.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Link to the Hub for active interaction 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • creation of knowledge and policies. • LET'S CARE databases, tools and Safe teaching Lab to impulse the implementation of Safe Education practices. • Specific documentation of data collection and project outputs
Communication strategy	Primarily orientated to generate awareness and information	Primarily oriented to enable know-how and active involvement in co-creation
Dissemination strategy	Focus on the dissemination of scientific and documental outputs	Focus on outreach and interactive dissemination in events, trainings, etc.

Table 1. Overview of differences between the Hub and website.

The website structure will be updated during the different phases of the project. The actual structure is as follows:

- **Home:** This page contains a general description of the project, its aims and the Consortium
- **Project:** This menu point has four subheadings from the drop-down menu:
 - *Community* with information about the Let's Care dynamisation bodies and structures.
 - *Research* presents the details on the LET'S CARE theoretical model and its methodology.
 - *Partners* introduces the partners of the project.
 - *Resources* has two subheadings available from the drop-down menu, "Project Resources" where deliverables produced in the scope of the LET'S CARE project will be uploaded, and "External Resources" where visitors can see other freely accessible, relevant resources in the topic of the project, not developed in the scope of LET'S CARE
- **Hub:** this menu point takes the user directly to the LET'S CARE Hub
- **Newsroom:** this menu point has five subheadings linking to:
 - *Latest news:* all the recent posts uploaded on the website.
 - *Events:* announcements or descriptions of the events related to the project organized or attended by the Consortium.
 - *Media corner:* communication, information and promotion materials like videos, fliers, infographics.
 - *Newsletter:* posting of the LET'S CARE newsletters.
 - *Training courses:* presentations of the training courses related to the project organized by the partners.
- **Privacy policy:** this section presents, in two subheadings, information related to the security and confidentiality issues on the website and on the social media.

Links to social media accounts of the project ([Facebook page](#), [Instagram](#), [Twitter](#) and [LinkedIn](#)) that will be used for communication and dissemination activities are also available at the bottom part of the website.

The website is fully responsive, available on any computer or mobile device. All the GDPR requirements have been met. Attending to the external assessment received we will consider merging the project website and HUB in future phases of the project.

3. LET'S CARE visual identity

3.1. Acronym of the project

LET'S CARE – the title of the project – has a double meaning:

- it recalls the action of taking care, the invitation to mind about the well-being of someone, in a participative and affective way;
- “LET’S” also refers to the pillars of the project: **L**Earner, **T**eacher and **S**chool.

3.2. Logo of the project

3.2.1. Concepts of the logo

LET'S CARE logo has been inspired by two main elements:

- **HANDS** representing the care and the safe environment.
- **CIRCLES** representing the Pillars and the levels considered by the project. The circles are intertwined, and they create new colours in the intersections, like in the reality the interconnection and the common actions of the different psycho-social levels results in a change in the person's life.

3.2.2. Logo Versions

Different logo versions will be used to be adapted to the contexts of use: with vertical or horizontal orientation, in .jpg / vectorial .pdf / .png versions. The versions are available in the project's repository. Some examples:

Figure 2 - Examples of project's logo with different orientations

3.3. Visibility of the European flag and funding statement

As stated in the article 17.2 of the Grant Agreement:

“Communication activities of the beneficiaries related to the action (including media relations, conferences, seminars, information material, such as brochures, leaflets, posters, presentations, etc., in electronic form, via traditional or social media, etc.), dissemination activities and any infrastructure, equipment, vehicles, supplies or major result funded by the grant must acknowledge EU support and display the European flag (emblem) and funding statement (translated into local languages, where appropriate)”

Figure 3 – Examples of EU funding logo with different orientations

Different formats and versions of the Emblem are available in the project's online repository.

Any communication or dissemination activity related to the action **must** indicate the following disclaimer (translated into local languages where appropriate):

“Funded by the European Union under grant agreement of the project 101059425. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them”.

3.4. Typography

3.4.1. Document Models for deliverables and presentations

A model for the deliverable and other official documents has been developed and is available in the project's online repository. The model of the document also contains the formatting style of the project: all the styles' names start with “_LETS” followed by the definition of the kind of paragraph so that the partners can identify them easily.

The template of the PowerPoint presentation is available in the project's online repository.

3.4.2. Fonts

Two main fonts will be used in the project's documents:

- Titles and headings: **Montserrat**

- Plain text: **Calibri Light**

The font used in the logo is **Kalam**.

It is possible to download the fonts at the following links:

- Montserrat: <https://fonts.google.com/download?family=Montserrat>
- Calibri Light: <https://www.cufonfonts.com/download/redirect/calibri-light>
- Kalam: <https://fonts.google.com/specimen/Kalam>

Montserrat:

LET'S CARE - Building Safe and Caring School to Foster Educational Inclusion and School Achievement

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Calibri Light:

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Kalam:

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3.5. Project's Colours

In the deliverables and communications about the project, it would be preferable to use the colours of the logo. The following table provides the codes of these colours.

Light Blue

RGB 116, 171, 224
CMYK 48, 24, 0, 12
74abe0

Dark Purple

RGB 94, 45, 142
CMYK 34, 68, 0, 44
5e2d8e

Light Purple

RGB 207, 48, 141
CMYK 0, 77, 32, 19
cf308d

Orange

RGB 215, 117, 54
CMYK 0, 46, 75, 16
#d77536

Moss Green

RGB 96, 94, 66
CMYK 0, 2, 31, 62
#605e42

Pink

RGB 218, 126, 172
CMYK 0, 42, 21, 15
#dA7eac